

D1.4 Data Management Plan

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Deliverable Information sheet

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1	15-12-2023	Jessica Snoek	eLEAF	Added comments from partners
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3	29-02-2024	Jessica Snoek	eLEAF	Final version for submission

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the data management life cycle for the data, from the data being collected, processed, and generated during the whole duration of the VitiGEOSS project. The purpose of this Data Management Plan is to establish how the data is created, stored and backed up. This document covers the handling of research data during and after the project, what data is collected, processed or generated, what methodology and standards is applied, whether data is shared/made open and how data is curated and preserved. The Data Management Plan is used as a standard data guideline for the project consortium to ensure interoperability and sharing of public data generated by the project.

Each project partner should respect the policies set out in the resulting Data Management Plan. Datasets must be created, managed, and stored appropriately and in line with European Commission and local legislation. Dataset validation and registration of metadata and backing up data for sharing through repositories is the responsibility of the partner that generates the data. The datasets in the repository project are preserved in line with the European Commission Data Deposit Policy.

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List of abbreviations

API	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
CSV	<i>Comma-Separated Values</i>
DMP	<i>Data Management Plan</i>
IPR	<i>Intellectual Property Rights</i>
JSON	<i>JavaScript Object Notation</i>
GRIB2	<i>GRIdded Binary edition 2</i>
NetCDF	<i>Network Common Data Form</i>
VITIGEOSS	<i>Vineyard Innovative Tool based on the InteGration of Earth Observation Services and in-field Sensors</i>
XLS	<i>Microsoft Excel spreadsheet file</i>
XML	<i>Extensible markup language</i>

1. Introduction

This document presents the fourth and final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the VitiGEOSS project. This deliverable, the VitiGEOSS data management plan, describes the (research) data that is collected and generated during the project and explains how it is exploited or if it is shared for verification and re-use.

The VitiGEOSS project aims to use European Open Earth Observation services for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental, and local level. To do so, the project developed an innovative vineyard management solution based on the integration of Earth Observation services and in-field sensors with the objective to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to the viticulture sector.

This process is visualized in figure 1, on the left all data inputs are displayed in green, satellite data, climate models, fixed cameras, in-field measurements and end-user information.

Figure 1. VitiGEOSS project data flow visualization.

The Data Management Plan describes how all data is managed, during the project and after it is finished. **Data management** refers to the everyday handling and workflow of research data during the active phase of a project as well as the practices that support long-term preservation, access, and use after the project has been completed. These activities can include planning, documenting data, formatting data, storing data, anonymizing data, and controlling access to data.

There are different stages in data management planning which are of importance and have an influence on how the data is collected, used, and stored. The stages as a cycle are displayed in figure 2.

Figure 2. Data Management Across VitiGEOSS Lifecycle

Discovery & Planning: This is the stage to determine what existing datasets can be of use in the VitiGEOSS projects and which has to be produced. Also, how to combine existing datasets or analyse existing datasets; identify privacy, confidentiality, and other ethical issues; consider documentation format and content and the metadata standards to use to describe the data; identify potential users of project data; identify an appropriate data repository to archive the data; and determine data management costs.

Initial Data Collection: This is the stage during which to determine workflows and procedures for organizing files, backups, and storage, performing quality assurance protocols, and setting appropriate access controls and security measures.

Preparation & Data Analysis: The collected data may not be the right fit to be input right away, it may need to be cleaned, manipulated, or processed. What is important during this stage is to document the changes to the raw data and create a “master” version to be analysed and eventually archived. It is also essential to document analysis procedures such as additional modifications to the data, the model used, the code used to run the analysis, and hardware and software specifications.

Publication and Sharing: This is the stage to consult with the archive or repository to determine file formats, clean and further document data. Additionally, all documentation should be reviewed to ensure that they contain enough information to allow the data to be re-used by a third party.

Long-term Management: During this stage researchers share their data and findings through publications, submit reports, and deposit data and supplementary materials into the archive or repository.

The Data Management Plan has been updated during the project lifetime, new versions of the This update is the third, and final, revision of the Data Management Plan.

2. Data collection

The VitiGEOSS data consists of multiple inputs from different sources over a period of three growing seasons. To ensure the accurate management of those different data streams the Data Management Plan is set in place. The VitiGEOSS system is designed to work with multiple data sources, decreasing risk of lack of data. If one data source is not available, it can easily be replaced with another one. Additionally, the focus lies on Mediterranean areas in which cloud cover is low during the grape production season.

Besides the use of GEOSS and Copernicus data, the field information is collected from three vineyards during the VitiGEOSS project. In Portugal the Quinta do Ataíde vineyard of the Symington Family Estates have been testing possible solutions, in Italy the Mirabella Eclano Estate owned by Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl served VitiGEOSS as a validation scenario, and in Spain the Torres family vineyard.

2.1 VitiGEOSS data

The purpose of the VitiGEOSS data collection is to provide forecasts, estimations, and recommendations to wine makers to optimize vineyard management processes. The innovative solution promoted by the project has the objective to respond to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which requires to intensify the production in a sustainable way, mitigate the effects of climate change, reduce negative environmental externalities, and promote local economic growth.

The three research plots are in important European viticultural regions (Douro, Portugal; Taurasi DOC areal, Italy; and Juneda, Lleida, Spain). Each pilot plot is of a minimum size of 1 ha and is managed according to the specific protocols adopted commercially by the end-users for wine making. This approach allowed to validate VitiGEOSS in different climate conditions, different cultivars, and viticultural strategies (different vineyard management protocols and different wine style goals).

The first six months of the VitiGEOSS project were used to select suitable plots at the three demo sites. The main selection criteria were vineyard exposition and slope, the cultivar, the intra-vineyard homogeneity (vines with similar age, vigour, rootstock, and training system, homogeneous soil, etc.), availability of a nearby weather station, availability of phenology data on the specific cultivars, and availability on historical management data. Once the pilot plots were identified, the setup of the pilot plots is finished with the installation of fixed cameras in the field, irrigation system adaptation if needed, installation of machinery data-loggers, acquisition of specific field equipment, etc., and the necessary vineyard modifications to be implemented.

The activities of the second task fine-tuned the calibration of the models included in VitiGEOSS. During the first vegetative season of the project, a high-quality dataset collected in the three selected vineyards have been used to tune the calibration of the downscaled weather forecast models, the phenological stage prediction models, the key crop indicators tracking models, the vine disease early warning system forecast, and the business and sustainability manager. An additional fine-tuning of the models have been realised between the vegetative seasons two and three.

The quantitative data resulted from all services have been provided in-season for operational use by end users via the VitiGEOSS portal in an automated way with the right frequency according to nature of the different services:

- Weather and climate: daily, weekly, and monthly
- Phenological: daily and monthly (field-based)

- Crop status: weekly, (field-based)
- Disease: daily, weekly & monthly on critical episodes (field-based)
- Business and sustainability: weekly/ (on demand) for optimization and plan of task and resources, monthly & yearly for sustainability indicators. (by using the appropriate parameters from the services)

The second and the third vegetative seasons of the project has been dedicated to fully validate the Intelligent Services that will run operationally, using data collected at the three demo sites. The performance of the VitiGEOSS services has been monitored, putting special emphasis on the validation of the business and sustainability services as well as the related dashboard (as final application integrating several intelligent services outputs) to confirm they could help the winemaking community to improve their current strategies to be more sustainable.

Data collected during second year has been used to calculate intermediate performance of intelligent services and proposing improvements to be implemented in the third year.

Data from the third year has been used to calculate final performance of the intelligent services This is done by evaluating the capacity of the tool in:

- forecasting the vine phenology
- monitoring the key crop indicators
- forecasting the occurrence of vine diseases
- delivering precise disease treatment recipes
- optimizing the use of resources and tasks
- evaluating sustainable indicators and implementing sustainability practices

2.2 Standards and methodologies

All data files are labelled and organized in a systematic way to make the data accessible for current and future users. As well as the naming of the files, this happens according to agreed conventions.

The data is collected by the service providers; they can upload and download data with VitiGEOSS services. The service providers collect, store, and maintain the data, the standards are different depending on the provider. A survey was conducted to collect information on methodologies used by the different service providers.

The survey provided an overview per service provider on the types and formats of data they generate throughout the project. The origin, interval and expected size of the data are noted. Regulations in place on how to share the data and what software is used to support this methodology are agreed upon among the consortium parties. These aspects are provider specific and overlap where needed within the project to support optimum collaboration. Lastly, security and responsibility of the data is agreed upon, the API architecture is set up so every service provider controls the security for their own service. The minimum security in place is agreed on among the providers and end-users. The survey on these details has been filled in by every service provider separately.

2.3 Best practices for file formats

Service providers delivered data in an agreed upon format during the project, the main formats are as followed:

Table 1. File formats organized based on data type.

Type of data	Format
Numerical data	Time series, excel, csv
Images	Images (e.g., jpeg)
Key crop indicators	JSON
Phenological phases	Geo TIFF, csv, JSON
Alerts, messages	Text, JSON
Model data	NetCDF, grib2

In table 2 below more detailed information can be found regarding the data which has been collected by service providers: Eurecat, BSC and LINKS.

Table 2. Service providers Eurecat, BSC and LINKS, type of data and format.

Service	Type of data collected	Type of data Generated	Data format
In-field repository	Machinery data from tractors and sensors on sprayers, weather stations data, images from fixed cameras, drone images (for the purpose of being stored by the service providers and offered to the rest of IS), historical data about (, weather stations, yield, disease treatments, phenological stages)	Machinery data from tractors and sensors on sprayers, weather stations data, images from fixed cameras, drone images, historical data	Time series; excel, csv, Json xml files, images
Disease management	Weather stations: real time data and historical data (Temperature, humidity, precipitation, wind speed, solar irradiation) Historical and actual treatments (date, dose, product used) Actual and forecasted phenology stages and dates. Forecasted weather variables (temperature, precipitation, wind speed, solar irradiation) Zonal delineation and crop health indicators Sprayers data	Disease risk assessment, alerts per parcel treatment and dosage recommendations per parcel based on disease risk	Text messages JSON data XLS, CSV files
Weather and climate forecasts	Weather forecast Sub-seasonal climate forecast Seasonal climate forecast	NNMB/MONARCH NCEP CFSv2 ECMWF SEAS5	NetCDF
Business and sustainability manager	Data from farm information systems (Pesticides, fertilizers, irrigation water, human labour,) Real-time farmer specifications in terms of harvest quantity, time available, or economy for logistical planning Machinery data	Task schedules Resource usage recommendations Sustainability KPIs	JSON XLS, CSV files

The size of the data is dependent on many factors such as frequency, resolution, area size, and more. Some data components are updated daily and provide information every three hours, others are checked weekly and give daily output. Not all data is collected using devices, but surveys and interviews with end-users and potential stakeholders are also an important knowledge base for the project. Data formats are flexible to change when agreed upon.

1. 2.4 Metadata per service provider

2.4.1 BSC - Weather and Climate

Resource Title	Short-term weather forecast	Sub-seasonal climate forecast	Seasonal climate forecast
<i>Temporal Reference</i> (YYYY-MM-DD till YYYY-MM-DD)	2021-07-06 till 2024-01-08	2017-01-05 till 2024-01-04	2021-06-01 till 2023-12-01
<i>Responsible organisation</i>	BSC	BSC	BSC
<i>E-mail</i>	nuria.perez@bsc.es	nuria.perez@bsc.es	nuria.perez@bsc.es
<i>Role</i>	Postdoctoral researcher	Postdoctoral researcher	Postdoctoral researcher
<i>Resource abstract</i>	MONARCH model output	Post-processed NCEP-CFSv2	Post-processed ECMWF SEAS5
<i>Keyword</i>	Extreme Weather	Climate Change Adaptation	Climate Change Adaptation
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	CC BY-NC-ND	CC BY-NC-ND	CC BY-NC-ND
<i>Limitations on public access</i> (access constraints)	BY: credit must be given to the creator. NC: Only noncommercial uses of the work are permitted. ND: No derivatives or adaptations of the work are permitted.	BY: credit must be given to the creator. NC: Only noncommercial uses of the work are permitted. ND: No derivatives or adaptations of the work are permitted.	BY: credit must be given to the creator. NC: Only noncommercial uses of the work are permitted. ND: No derivatives or adaptations of the work are permitted.
<i>Limitations on public access</i> (other constraints)			
<i>Limitations on public access</i> (classification)			
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset</i> (Equivalent scale)	~0.1°x0.1°	0.1°x 0.1°	0.1°x 0.1°
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>			
<i>Geographic bounding box (west)</i>	-62.95°E	Catalonia -1°E; Douro: -9°E; Campania: 13°E	Catalonia -1°E; Douro: -9°E; Campania: 13°E
<i>Geographic bounding box (east)</i>	101.95°E	Catalonia 4°E; Douro: -6°E; Campania: 17.3°E	Catalonia 4°E; Douro: -6°E; Campania: 17.3°E
<i>Geographic bounding box (south)</i>	-10.95°N	Catalonia 40°N; Douro: 40°N; Campania: 39°N	Catalonia 40°N; Douro: 40°N; Campania: 39°N
<i>Geographic bounding box (north)</i>	71.45°N	Catalonia 44°N; Douro: 43°N; Campania: 43°N	Catalonia 44°N; Douro: 43°N; Campania: 43°N
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	NetCDF	NetCDF	NetCDF

2.4.1 eLEAF - Key Crop Indicators

Resource Title	NDVI	LAI	Biomass Production	Evapotranspiration
<i>Responsible organisation</i>	eLEAF	eLEAF	eLEAF	eLEAF
<i>E-mail</i>	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com
<i>Role</i>	PM	PM	PM	PM
<i>Resource abstract</i>				
<i>Keyword</i>	Vegetation Index	Vegetation Index	Biomass	Evapotranspiration
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (access constraints)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (other constraints)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (classification)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset (Equivalent scale)</i>	10m	10m	10m	10m
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>	Farming	Farming	Farming	Farming
<i>Geographic bounding box (Symington)</i>	-7.538027,41.190668,-7.108397,41.251719			
<i>Geographic bounding box (Torres)</i>	0.8212433, 41.4856105, 0.8362767,41.5060997			
<i>Geographic bounding box (Mastroberardino)</i>	14.8846576131573194, 40.9250104370603367, 15.0363183377689502, 41.0682625724365735			
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	Shapefile	Shapefile	Shapefile	Shapefile

Resource Title	Potential Evapotranspiration	Nitrogen in canopy	Nitrogen in upper leaf	Yield forecast	Crop Water Demand
Responsible organisation	eLEAF	eLEAF	eLEAF	eLEAF	eLEAF
<i>E-mail</i>	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com	jessica.snoek@eleaf.com
<i>Role</i>	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
<i>Resource abstract</i>					
<i>Keyword</i>	Evapotranspiration	Nitrogen	Nitrogen	Yield	Water forecast
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (access constraints)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (other constraints)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (classification)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset (Equivalent scale)</i>	10m	10m	10m	10m	10m
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>	Farming	Farming	Farming	Farming	Farming
<i>Geographic bounding box (Symington)</i>	-7.538027,41.190668,-7.108397,41.251719				
<i>Geographic bounding box (Torres)</i>	0.8212433, 41.4856105, 0.8362767,41.5060997				
<i>Geographic bounding box (Mastroberardino)</i>	14.8846576131573194, 40.9250104370603367, 15.0363183377689502, 41.0682625724365735				
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	Shapefile	Shapefile	Shapefile	Shapefile	Shapefile

2.4.1 LINKS - Phenology

<i>Resource Title</i>	Historical Symington Phenology 2017-2023
<i>Temporal Reference (YYYY-MM-DD till YYYY-MM-DD)</i>	2017-01-01 till 2023-12-31
<i>Responsible organisation</i>	Symington
<i>E-mail</i>	fernando.alves@symington.com
<i>Role</i>	owner
<i>Resource abstract</i>	This resource contains historical phenology data obtained between 2017 and 2023. The collected phenological observations are classified based on the Baggiolini scale, focusing on distinct phases crucial to viticulture: bud break, blooming, fruit set, veraison, ripening, and leaf fall. These observations were meticulously recorded and analyzed on specifically selected fields on the grapevine varieties of Touriga Franca and Touriga Nacional in Douro Valley (Portugal).
<i>Keyword</i>	Agricultural And Aquaculture Facilities, Climate Change Adaptation
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (access constraints)</i>	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (other constraints)</i>	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (classification)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset (Equivalent scale)</i>	point
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>	farming
<i>Geographic bounding box</i>	-7.538027,41.190668,-7.108397,41.251719
<i>Geographic bounding box (east)</i>	
<i>Geographic bounding box (south)</i>	
<i>Geographic bounding box (north)</i>	
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	excel

<i>Resource Title</i>	Historical Torres Phenology 2017-2023
<i>Temporal Reference (YYYY-MM-DD till YYYY-MM-DD)</i>	2017-01-01 till 2023-12-31
<i>Responsible organisation</i>	Torres
<i>E-mail</i>	mtorresv@torres.es
<i>Role</i>	owner
<i>Resource abstract</i>	This resource contains historical phenology data obtained between 2017 and 2023 within the scope of the VITIGEOSS project (ID: 869565). The collected phenological observations are classified based on the Baggiolini scale, focusing on distinct phases crucial to viticulture: bud break, blooming, fruit set, veraison, ripening, and leaf fall. These observations were meticulously recorded and analyzed on specifically selected fields on the grapevine varieties of Syrah in Catalonia (Spain).
<i>Keyword</i>	Agricultural And Aquaculture Facilities, Climate Change Adaptation
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (access constraints)</i>	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (other constraints)</i>	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (classification)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset (Equivalent scale)</i>	point
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>	farming
<i>Geographic bounding box</i>	0.8212433, 41.4856105, 0.8362767,41.5060997
<i>Geographic bounding box (east)</i>	
<i>Geographic bounding box (south)</i>	
<i>Geographic bounding box (north)</i>	
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	excel

<i>Resource Title</i>	Historical Mastroberardino Phenology 2017-2023
<i>Temporal Reference</i> (YYYY-MM-DD till YYYY-MM-DD)	2017-01-01 till 2023-12-31
<i>Responsible organisation</i>	UNINA, Mastroberardino
<i>E-mail</i>	boris.basile@unina.it
<i>Role</i>	owner
<i>Resource abstract</i>	This resource contains historical phenology data obtained between 2017 and 2023 within the scope of the VITIGEOSS project (ID: 869565). The collected phenological observations are classified based on the Baggiolini scale, focusing on distinct phases crucial to viticulture: bud break, blooming, fruit set, veraison, ripening, and leaf fall. These observations were meticulously recorded and analyzed on specifically selected fields on the grapevine varieties of Aglianico and Greco, in Irpinia region, South of Italy.
<i>Keyword</i>	Agricultural And Aquaculture Facilities, Climate Change Adaptation
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (access constraints)</i>	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (other constraints)</i>	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (classification)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset (Equivalent scale)</i>	point
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>	farming
<i>Geographic bounding box</i>	14.8846576131573194, 40.9250104370603367, 15.0363183377689502, 41.0682625724365735
<i>Geographic bounding box (east)</i>	
<i>Geographic bounding box (south)</i>	
<i>Geographic bounding box (north)</i>	
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	excel

2.4.1 Eurecat - Disease

<i>Resource Title</i>	Historical Symington diseases 2021-2023	Historical Torres diseases 2021-2023	Historical Mastroberardino diseases 2021-2023
<i>Temporal Reference (YYYY-MM-DD till YYYY-MM-DD)</i>	2021-01-01 till 2023-12-31	2021-01-01 till 2023-12-31	2021-01-01 till 2023-12-31
<i>Responsible organisation</i>	Symington	Torres	Mastroberardino
<i>E-mail</i>	fernando.alves@symington.com	mtorresv@torres.es	Dente@mastroberardino.com
<i>Role</i>	owner	owner	owner
<i>Resource abstract</i>	Symington's disease data for 2021 to 2023. This dataset includes data of disease apparition, % of incidence, % of severity, used fungicide, and dosage.	Torres' disease data for 2021 to 2023. This dataset includes data of disease apparition, % of incidence, % of severity, used fungicide, and dosage.	Mastroberardino's disease data for 2021 to 2023. This dataset includes data of disease apparition, % of incidence, % of severity, used fungicide, and dosage.
<i>Keyword</i>	Fungal Disease, Vulnerability, Natural Risk Zones	Fungal Disease, Vulnerability, Natural Risk Zones	Fungal Disease, Vulnerability, Natural Risk Zones
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (access constraints)</i>	Limited	Limited	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (other constraints)</i>	Limited	Limited	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (classification)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset (Equivalent scale)</i>	parcel	parcel	parcel
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>	farming	farming	farming
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	excel	excel	excel

2.4.1 Eurecat - Sustainability

<i>Resource Title</i>	Historical Symington sustainability 2021-2023	Historical Torres sustainability 2021-2023	Historical Mastroberardino sustainability 2021-2023
<i>Temporal Reference (YYYY-MM-DD till YYYY-MM-DD)</i>	2021-01-01 till 2023-12-31	2021-01-01 till 2023-12-31	2021-01-01 till 2023-12-31
<i>Responsible organisation</i>	Symington	Torres	Mastroberardino
<i>E-mail</i>	fernando.alves@symington.com	mtorresv@torres.es	Dente@mastroberardino.com
<i>Role</i>	owner	owner	owner
<i>Resource abstract</i>	This resource contains the information regarding Symington's sustainability KPIs calculated for the years 2021 to 2023, The KPIs contain information about productivity, water usage, yield, pesticide usage, CO2 emissions, usage of human resources, and business data.	This resource contains the information regarding Torres' sustainability KPIs calculated for the years 2021 to 2023, The KPIs contain information about productivity, water usage, yield, pesticide usage, CO2 emissions, usage of human resources, and business data.	This resource contains the information regarding Mastroberardino's sustainability KPIs calculated for the years 2021 to 2023, The KPIs contain information about productivity, water usage, yield, pesticide usage, CO2 emissions, usage of human resources, and business data., and business data.
<i>Keyword</i>	Energy Resources, Environmental Monitoring Facilities, Key Performance Indicator, Climate Change Adaptation	Energy Resources, Environmental Monitoring Facilities, Key Performance Indicator, Climate Change Adaptation	Energy Resources, Environmental Monitoring Facilities, Key Performance Indicator, Climate Change Adaptation
<i>Conditions applying to access and use</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Limitations on public access (access constraints)</i>	Limited	Limited	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (other constraints)</i>	Limited	Limited	Limited
<i>Limitations on public access (classification)</i>	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner	closed dataset - contact the owner
<i>Spatial resolution of the dataset (Equivalent scale)</i>	parcel	parcel	parcel
<i>Dataset topic category (ISO)</i>	environment	environment	environment
<i>Distribution format [Encoding]</i>	excel	excel	excel

3. Ethics and legal compliance

All beneficiaries involved in the VitiGEOSS project strive for balance and equal opportunities, this is related to gender, age, nationality, etc. Attention is paid to a balanced distribution of gender, age, and country of origin in composing the advisory board and the consortium.

Data collection, storage and possibilities of sharing in the future are agreed upon by all beneficiaries who are part of the VitiGEOSS project. With the data architecture put in place during the project every service provider has control and responsibility over their own data, they create, store and share data. They all carry the responsibility to do so according to the standards set in this plan. Moving forward, after the duration of the project, the architecture will remain in place. This API architecture will allow for services to be flexible, in control of their own data, and for every provider to secure the quality and requirements they adhere to.

This architecture is the result of “*Subtask 3.2.1: Set up the API service store to establish connections with the individual service providers.*” This task has been finalized with the setting up of the API service store. Details on the storage and security details of the API service store are listed in Chapter 7.

In every detail of the VitiGEOSS service the GDPR is considered, this goes for the VitiGEOSS services, documents, communication and research activities. When accessing the platform.vitigeoss.eu, the webpage which allows you to log into the VitiGEOSS platform refers to the Terms and Conditions which explain the compliance in place for the platform.

The API service store is located in the eLEAF server environment, this secure data environment runs according to GDPR standards; securing the personal data of EU individuals in connection with either the offering of goods or services to data subjects in the EU or the monitoring of behaviour that takes place within the EU. Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person, including names, email addresses and phone numbers.

Recovery procedures for the eLEAF server environment protect the data from any possible risks, the location of the servers and the back-up procedures are all organized according to state-of-the-arts measures put in place.

4. Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues

The VitiGEOSS Project produces data assets such as an application portal; Task 5.2., Work Package 5, Deliverable 5.2. This task oversees the management of all intellectual property that will arise from the project and will take the necessary steps to ensure that it can be appropriately protected.

IP experts from EUT support partners in the identification of Exploitable results - a project results table has been developed to identify, synchronize, and conduct efficient IP planning and management, including ownership rights.

Exploitation managers have been assigned to each result and the management of the collective project foreground are a part of periodic reporting and project meetings. IP strategies -

Regular patent surveillance has been undertaken in relation to relevant exploitable results. This allows a correct management of future patentability processes (e.g., confirm novelty, inventive step, industrial application) and ensure "Freedom to Operate" for future commercial products/services.

Throughout the duration of the project, there were a total of 42 months allocated for the enhancement of the existing models utilizing Earth observation data. Additionally, validation processes have been conducted across three growing seasons, showcasing the progress through demonstrations on end-user plots.

Nevertheless, special agreements may be made with end users (Symington, Mirabella Eclano Estate and Torres) for a longer fine-tuning of the platform.

5. Sharing the data and OPENDATA

Data sharing among partners throughout the project is done by using SharePoint and THREDDS.

During the term of VitiGEOSS, Zenodo is used to share the public results with those interested. Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository which contains scientific publications and data. Sharing data and making the research as open as possible can be realized through this, the Zenodo page for VitiGEOSS is: https://zenodo.org/communities/869565_vitigeoss/.

During the project we have been in touch with GeoPortal.org, however, we have not successfully managed to share VitiGEOSS' metadata on the platform. If this becomes a possibility after the project conclusion we will do so.

The VitiGEOSS project aims to use European Open Earth Observation services for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental, and local level. The commercial innovation and market penetration is work package 5, first an extensive market assessment has been conducted. Followed by a market analysis and competitive assessment, focusing specifically on the wine sector in Europe. Critical success factors and other outcomes of the first steps will form for the assessment of the VitiGEOSS potential market acceptance. This process and its results will determine in what way the data comes together and be shared.

6. Roles and responsibilities

All nine parties in the VitiGEOSS project have their own role and responsibilities during the project. These roles and their responsibilities are all documented in the ‘Description of Action’ of the VitiGEOSS project.

Each partner is responsible for the data generated from his/her institution as data producers, proper data collection, documentation, and storage throughout the duration of the project, under the supervision of their respective data protection officers. Specific agreements may be signed among partners to grant access to the different datasets for the different uses.

The VitiGEOSS platform is a complex project with the intervention multiple actors with different data inputs, an exhaustive analysis regarding the data management procedures are conducted further in the project.

Table 3. List of beneficiaries and their role in the VitiGEOSS project.

Name	Lead beneficiary for WP	Role
Eurecat	WP 1: Project management, WP 2: Intelligent (information) services on vineyard management	Service Provider
Fondazione Links		Service Provider
eLEAF	WP 3: Integrated Vineyard Management Application Portal (DSS)	Service Provider
Barcelona Supercomputing Center	WP 6: Communication & Dissemination	Service Provider
Price Waterhouse Coopers /Ag - Assessoria de Gestao	WP 5: Commercial Innovation and market penetration	Service Provider
Universita Degli Studi Di Napoli Federico II	WP 4: Demonstration	Service Provider
Symington Family Estates		End-user
Aziende Vinicola Michele Mastroberardino SPA		End-user
Miguel Torres SA		End-user

All partners are responsible for the treatment of the data on their own premises, and all partners have their own security measures in place to avoid any possible threats, the storage and security in place are shared in the next chapter. An API connection is set up to share data.

Quality assurance is a shared responsibility between and among partners. Quality Assurance is monitored by thorough checks and tests that are conducted throughout the course of the project to realize the highest possible quality. The quality checks focus on the specified and updated requirements during the project, from start to end. These specified requirements are discussed, documented, and approved before design, implementation, and delivery.

7. Storage and security

The service providers collect, store, and maintain the data. The standards are dependant of the type and quantity of the data, so they are different depending on the service provider. Data sharing among partners throughout the project is done by using SharePoint, the VitiGEOSS API, and THREDDS.

Data can be retrieved using the API developed by the consortium partner that owns the API. Data is also stored in a SQL database within a server in the partner's environment. To access the server, connecting via VPN, for which credentials are required, and with a second-layer authentication to log on. Data can be retrieved using the VitiGEOSSAPI developed by each of the service providers. To access the desired data, a specific token is required for each user and provides selective access, preventing the leakage of sensitive data.

The data being stored in a safe environment, the eLEAF server environment, allows only authorized personnel to access. This is controlled with the support of password protection, verified IP addresses and by recording access to servers. Backups are taken periodically, and a restoration process is established in case of a failure.

Every service provider has set up an API which connects with the overall VitiGEOSS API service store. The API service store is a cloud-based application portal which forms a repository of consortium intelligent services that enables the connection of these data-services to the VitiGEOSS application available to the end-user. It encompasses the data service repository, metadata management and API manager to form a repository of intelligent services, which will enable the connection between these data services and the VitiGEOSS application available to the end-users on a public website eventually.

The API service manages access control, authentication, authorization of services, of data, users of the API service store and eventually users of the VITIGE OSS application. The API Service Store is composed of a data service repository, with an extra interface for Partners to add, manage and control all API's created, and an authentication/authorization application and API configurator. This entails the overall authorization/authentication/access control of services, of data, of users/partners in the API store. For more detailed information regarding the API service, see deliverable 3.2 Deployment of the VITIGE OSS cloud-based application portal.

